

The Market System of Small-Scale Vegetables Production on Product Marketability

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ABSTRACT

The study, entitled “The Market System of Small-scale Vegetable Production on Product Marketability” examines the increasing global concerns about food security and sustainable agriculture, small-scale vegetable production plays a vital role in strengthening national food systems and rural livelihoods. This study assessed the market system of small-scale vegetable production and its influence on product marketability in San Isidro, Nueva Ecija, Philippines. Anchored on Institutional Organizational Theory and Porters’ Five Forces Model, the research examined how institutional environments and competitive forces shape the farmers’ ability to market their produce effectively.

Utilizing a descriptive-survey method, data were gathered from a total of 100 small-scale vegetable farmers through a complete enumeration of the target population and through the use of statistical tools such as weighted mean and Spearman’s rank Correlation Coefficient to analyze the data. Despite the strategic relevance of institutional and market-related factors, statistical analysis revealed no significant correlation between the market system and product marketability, leading to the retention of the null hypothesis. These findings suggest that while external and institutional factors are present, other variables may play a more critical role in influencing market success. The study highlights the need for further investigation into internal farm-level capabilities and policy support mechanisms to enhance the competitiveness and sustainability of small-scale vegetable farming.

1. Introduction

In a time when food security and sustainable agriculture are becoming global priorities small-scale vegetable production becomes an essential component of national food systems and rural livelihoods. Globally the trend for organic locally grown, and fresh food is changing consumer habits and market dynamics. It highlights the essentials of agricultural systems that promote equal economic growth and environmental sustainability.

The economy of the Philippines is heavily reliant on agriculture, which supports food supply structures and employs a significant portion of the workforce. However, small-scale vegetable farmers encounter several barriers that prevent them from reaching profitable markets, despite their essential role. As an alternative source of income farmers in provinces like Nueva Ecija which known as the “Rice Granary of the Philippines,” are now turning to vegetable growing. The market institutional assistance, price fluctuation, and competition, however, are frequently issues for these farmers.

From a personal perspective many smallholders lack the technical knowledge, financial capital, and strategic guidance needed to make their produce competitive. From a legal and policy view, while the Philippine government has implemented various agricultural development programs under frameworks like the “Agriculture and Fisheries Modernization Act” and “Republic Act 8435,” gaps remain in the lack of understanding of how institutional support and market conditions together affect the ability of small- scale vegetable farmers to sell their products successfully.

This study aims to examine the market system managing small-scale vegetable production, studying the impact of institutional scenarios, competition, and organizational behavior on the ability of farmers to market their products. This study examines the effect of external factors including the institutional environment, isomorphism, institutional logic, and institutional change, together with competitive pressures such as the threat of new entrants and substitutes, the bargaining power of buyers and suppliers, and rivalry among existing competitors, by way of a combination of Institutional

Organizational Theory and Porter's Five Forces Model.

Understanding these interactions is essential for developing successful strategies such as strengthening local market interactions by establishing farmer cooperatives or associations that enhance collective bargaining power and access to regional markets, enhancing technical and business training through regular capacity building initiatives focused on sustainable farming practices, crop planning, post-harvest management, and value addition, Lastly promoting for digital and online market platforms that encourage the use of mobile devices and social media therefore connecting farmers directly with buyers, consumers, and retailers to improve the profitability and sustainability of small-scale vegetable farming. Additionally, support for digital and online market platforms that promote the use of mobile devices and social media, there by connect farmers directly with buyers, consumers, and retailers to enhance the profitability and sustainability of small-scale vegetable farming.

This study aims to bridge production and commercialization, inform policy, guide local stakeholders and empower farmers with practical tools for market success.

2. Research Method

2.1 Research Design

Quantitative research design and descriptive-survey method of research was used in this study.

According to Best and Kahn (2007), the descriptive method of research means: "The term descriptive research has often been misused to describe three types of investigation that are different.

According to Dr YP Aggarwal (2008), descriptive research is devoted to the gathering of information about prevailing conditions or situations for description and interpretation.

2.2 Participants

The researchers used convenience sampling, to choose the respondents, who were directly involved in the production and distribution of a variety of vegetables, making them suitable sources of data to study the local market system. 100 small-scale vegetable farmers from San Isidro, Nueva Ecija a municipality known for its strong agricultural presence, participated in this study as respondents. The convenience sampling allows us to focus on people who can provide the most relevant and detailed insights on the market system affecting product marketability, resulting in significant and focused results in our study.

2.3 Instrumentation

The researcher used a survey questionnaire and the "Institutional Organizational Theory" of John W. Meyer and Brian Rowan, as well as Porter's Five Forces by Michael E. Porter, to determine the respondents' response to the marketability strategies. Part one of the questionnaires consists of the demographic profile of the respondents. Part two comprises the external factors that influence and affect the market system of small-scale vegetable production, including Institutional Environments, Isomorphism, Institutional Logics, and Institutional Change. To show the respondents' level of agreement, the researchers used the 5-point Likert scale where (1) strongly disagree; (2) disagree; (3) somewhat agree; (4) agree; and (5) strongly agree. Part three of the questionnaire describes the factors of product marketability of small-scale vegetable production in terms of Threat of new entrants, Threat of substitutes, Bargaining powers of buyers, Bargaining power of suppliers, and Rivalry among existing competitors.

2.4 Validation of Instrument

The instrument used in the study of "The Market System of Small-Scale Vegetable Production on Product Marketability" was checked to ensure clarity, accuracy and reliability. This process is conducted to ensure that the research instrument accurately measures the variables, ensuring the production of reliable and accurate information.

2.5 Data Gathering Procedures

The researcher seeks approval to survey the market system of small-scale vegetable production on product marketability.

Upon receipt of the approval letter, 100 questionnaires were photocopied for distribution to the participants. Some verbal instructions for clarity followed the administration of the questionnaires. It took the researchers 14 days to collect 100 questionnaires. The participants were busy at the time of data gathering.

2.6 Analysis of Data

The information gathered in this study was arranged and used the research design as a guide. The study used Likert scale, weighted mean, and

Spearman's rho correlation as instruments for data collection, interpretation, and analysis. Each of these tools served a specific purpose in clarifying the marketing strategies employed by small-scale vegetable farmers.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter contained a detailed presentation and discussion of data analysis and the findings from 100 questionnaires completed by small-scale farmers in San Isidro, Nueva Ecija. The survey's data were provided in tabular form with supporting interpretations, conclusions, and theoretical underpinnings.

Table 1

Respondents' Level of Agreement on the Market System of Small-Scale Vegetable Production

External Factors Influence and Affect the Marketability of Small-Scale Vegetable Production	WM	VI
Institutional Environment	3.81	Agree
Isomorphism	3.97	Agree
Institutional Logics	4.07	Agree
Institutional Change	3.99	Agree
Overall	3.96	Agree

Legend: Strongly Agree; 4.21 - 5.00, Agree; 4.20 – 3.41, Somewhat Agree; 3.40 – 2.61, Disagree; 2.60 – 1.81, Strongly Disagree; 1.80 – 1.00

Table 1 summarizes the respondents' level of agreement on how various external institutional factors influence the marketability of small-scale vegetable production. The consolidated categories received a verbal interpretation of "agree", with an overall weighted mean of 3.96, shows that respondents think that these outside variables help them sell their produce. In terms of institutional environment with a 3.81 weighted mean, isomorphism with a 3.97 weighted mean, institutional logics with a 4.07 weighted mean, and institutional change with a 3.99 weighted mean.

Table 2

Respondents' Level of Agreement on Factors of Market System Influence Product Marketability of Small-Scale Vegetable Production

Respondents' Level of Agreement on Factors of Market System Influence Product Marketability of Small-Scale Vegetable Production	WM	VI
Threats of new entrants	3.94	Agree
Threat of Substitute	3.92	Agree
Bargaining power of buyers	4.01	Agree
Bargaining power of suppliers	4.03	Agree
Rivalry among existing competitors	3.99	Agree
Overall	3.98	Agree

Legend: Strongly Agree; 4.21 - 5.00, Agree; 4.20 – 3.41, Somewhat Agree; 3.40 – 2.61, Disagree; 2.60 – 1.81, Strongly Disagree; 1.80 – 1.00

Table 2 data indicate that all five forces under Porter's five forces are perceived by small-scale vegetable farmers as influential to the marketability of their produce, with overall agreement reflected in an average weighted mean of 3.98, and are generally interpreted as "agree". In terms of threats of new entrants with a 3.94 weighted mean, threats of substitute with a 3.92 weighted mean, bargaining power of buyers with the weighted mean of 4.01,

bargaining power of suppliers with a weighted mean of 4.03, and rivalry among existing competitors with a weighted mean of 3.99.

Table 3

Significant correlation between the market system and product marketability of small-scale vegetable production.

INDICATORS	P-VALUE	DECISION	CONCLUSION
Institutional Environment	0.1868	Retain Ho	Not Significant
Isomorphism	0.0262	Reject Ho	Significant
Institutional Logics	0.034	Reject Ho	Significant
Institutional Change	0.143	Retain Ho	Not Significant
Overall	0.098	Reject Ho	Not Significant

Legend: If P-Value=<0.05–Reject Ho (Significant); If P-Value>0.05–Accept Ho (Not Significant)

Table 3 results revealed that Isomorphism ($p = 0.0262$) and Institutional Logics ($p = 0.034$) had p-values below 0.05, which led to the rejection of the null hypothesis and indicated a significant influence on marketability. In contrast, Institutional Environment ($p = 0.1868$) and Institutional Change ($p = 0.143$) had p-values above 0.05, resulting in the retention of the null hypothesis and were considered not significant. Results recommend that only some aspects of Isomorphism and Institutional Logics directly affected the marketability of small-scale vegetable production. However, the overall p-value was 0.098, which led to the retention of the null hypothesis and concluded a “Not Significant” overall relationship between market system and product marketability.

4. Conclusion

The following were the conclusions extracted from the findings above:

- 4.1 The respondents agreed on the market system of small-scale vegetable production in terms of Institutional Environment, Isomorphism, Institutional Logic, and Institutional Change.
- 4.2 The respondents agreed on the factors of market system influence product marketability of small-scale vegetable production in terms of Threat of New Entrants, Threat of Substitutes, Bargaining Power of Buyers, Bargaining Power of Suppliers, and Rivalry among Existing Competitors.
- 4.3 The researchers failed to reject the null hypothesis and found no significant correlation between the market system and the product marketability of small-scale vegetable production. But in terms of Isomorphism and Institutional Logics, they were found to be significant and led to rejecting the null hypothesis.

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